

Intersectional Solidarity: The Importance of Women in Canadian Educational Leadership Coming Together Over Time

Sharlene McHolm (Adjunct Professor - Wilfrid Laurier University)

Carolina Miranda (independent researcher)

Abstract:

Education is often considered the single most important indicator of a nation's progress and promise. Education acts to offer opportunity and optimism for those that have not been born to wealth and privilege. Yet without thoughtful awareness, school systems can continue to perpetuate disadvantage – unless there is a leader willing to see the promise in everyone. Strong educational leadership is required to fortify the growth realized by individuals and push the boundaries forward from promise to actualization. It is an accepted fact that educational leadership is second only to teacher impact on student achievement, graduation rates, and attendance. Kind, intelligent and thoughtful leadership influences teacher retention rates, equity affirming practices and school cultures. In Canada, one of the most liberal countries in the world, continues to see difference in leadership opportunities for women, particularly those from equity deserving communities. This article takes a bi-ethnographic exploration of the journey of two school leaders with differing positionality but a shared goal of school leadership diversification.

Key Words: equity-deserving, equity, school leadership, women, shared leadership

Education is often considered the single most important indicator of a nation's progress and promise. Education acts to offer opportunity and optimism for those that have not been born to wealth and privilege. Yet without thoughtful awareness, school systems can continue to perpetuate disadvantage – unless there is a leader willing to see the promise in everyone. Strong educational leadership is required to fortify the growth realized by individuals and push the boundaries forward from promise to actualization (Moore, 2024). It is an accepted fact that educational leadership is second only to teacher impact on student achievement, graduation rates, and attendance (Darling-Hammond, 2024; Leithwood & Sun, 2018). Kind, intelligent and thoughtful leadership influences teacher retention rates, equity affirming practices and school cultures (Darling-Hammond et al., 2024). Therefore, having the right people in the right leadership positions are essential in order to ensure student growth and generational prosperity. Despite the fact that education has been growing into a female dominated field, women in leadership have lagged behind, particularly in secondary schools and district level positions. Further still, behind gender gaps in educational leadership, other forms of intersectionality represent a loss in the learning environment for all. It is only through the shared approach of collaboration, care and mutual support that women and

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women with equity deserving intersectionalities must come together to foster the dynamic learning environments needed for a prosperous future.

History of Gender in Canadian Educational Leadership

The history of women in educational leadership is a relatively short one, even in a liberal country such as Canada. In the middle of the twentieth century, despite the fact that the majority of teachers were women, few made the ranks of leadership. In Toronto in 1940, 4% of elementary principals were women. By 1980, that number had risen to 14%, with 13% of high schools being led by women (Reynolds et al., 2008). To be a leader and a woman, choices had to be made. Remaining single or if married, to be childless were the norms for women leaders. The “double bind” of an untenable tension between gender roles and stereotypes made leadership for all women difficult. By the end of the century, as more women entered the role of school leadership, secondary schools continued to lag in their leadership presence. Those that did follow that path were often stereotyped as being too emotional for the role or too lenient or too aggressive to be a kind woman. When I, Sharlene, entered the role as a high school vice principal at the turn of the century, it was before having children. Those women in secondary leadership roles around me were later in their careers and were generally post their “child bearing years”. I knew of only one other female principal with a somewhat young family, but none that wanted to take parental leave while in the role. I, being young and female, while starting a family was an anomaly. There were many male colleagues at a similar stage, but the implications to leadership and advancement were experienced differently. When I came back to the role, my district placed me at a school geographically distant from my home, leading me to make the decision to leave that district. At the time, I did not feel like a trailblazer as there were women in leadership around me. I felt proud to be one of the few women in the room, but I did not understand how gender and family should not have impacted me differently than my male counterparts.

Fast forward twenty years, and although the landscape of education had changed remarkably, alongside the demographics of Canada, much had remained the same within Ontario school leadership. In 2020, OPC (Ontario’s Principal Council), representing Ontario’s public schools’ practicing principals and vice principals, surveyed their school leaders. Progress had not advanced as we might have hoped. At that time, school leaders were of White/European origins 83% of the time despite only representing 68% of the general population. Ninety-two percent of respondents identified as heterosexual and 68% identified as female (Turner, 2021). Although we had reached the tipping point of gender representation (albeit slightly lower than the 75.7% women teachers) (Statistics Canada, 2024) we had made little gains towards true representation of students in front of us at our schools. Within the 2020’s truer equity has thrust forward in pockets and districts in Ontario. Particularly in my corner of South Western Ontario I have grown to rely on the diverse voices above me and beside me at the table. Their wisdom and insight grounds my understanding and allows me to serve my schools in a deeper and more compassionate way.

Compounding Challenges of Intersectionality in Canadian Educational Leadership

Understanding intersectionality is essential to recognizing the leadership practices of racialized women in education. Crenshaw (1989) defined intersectionality as the way gender, race, and class intersect to shape unique experiences of oppression and privilege. In educational leadership, this perspective reveals both barriers and opportunities, promoting social justice and transformative leadership (Murakami et al., 2018; Wilkinson & McDonald, 2022).

Research by Grogan and Shakeshaft (2011) shows that in general, women often lead with a focus on social justice, relational leadership, and student learning while balancing professional and personal responsibilities. This is not in any way misaligned with the specific experiences of racialized women who navigate systemic biases related to both race and gender. Showumni (2021) highlights the challenges of stereotypes, microaggressions, and professional isolation. I, Carolina, have personally experienced the “double disadvantage” of sexism and racism, which has sometimes undermined my authority and limited my career progression. The pressure to code-switch — altering how I dress, speak, and present myself — has played a role in how I am perceived or accepted, yet it has often felt stifling.

Despite these challenges, racialized women play a transformative role in educational leadership. Our lived experiences foster innovative approaches to leadership, allowing us to challenge oppressive practices and amplify marginalized voices (Showumni, 2021; Murakami et al., 2018). By connecting to culture, land, and historical oppression, we bring diverse perspectives that enrich school environments and disrupt dominant leadership models often shaped by white, heteronormative, and masculinist frameworks (Wilkinson & McDonald, 2022).

Intersectional solidarity is essential. While I, Carolina, have experienced harm from some white women, it would be dismissive of me to not acknowledge that many of my greatest mentors have also been racialized women, as well as white women who were committed to allyship, mentorship, and guidance. Their support has helped me navigate systemic barriers and advance my career. As gatekeepers within educational systems, white women who choose to act as allies can create more inclusive spaces by advocating for equity and challenging discrimination. Showumni (2021) notes that professional jealousy can arise among women leaders, yet solidarity remains crucial. As a racialized woman myself, I have also encountered jealousy from other racialized women, which highlights the complexities of these dynamics.

Intersectionality shapes our identities as leaders. Murakami et al. (2018) found that Latina/o school administrators often use their cultural backgrounds to connect with students of colour, fostering trust and engagement. As a Latina principal, my cultural background helps me advocate for diverse

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student populations, promoting equity and belonging. Even when my background differs from my students', I can empathize with their cultural struggles, creating an authentic foundation for our relationships. Additionally, racialized leaders serve as role models, demonstrating that success within the educational ecosystem is possible despite the current systemic barriers, and inspiring future generations to pursue educational leadership.

Wilkinson and McDonald (2022) argue that fully harnessing the potential of intersectional leadership requires grounding this work in Black feminist theories, which prioritize anti-oppression and social transformation. Black feminism resists the “whitening” of its political potential, promoting counter-hegemonic knowledge and non-oppressive coalitions. By embracing this framework, educational leaders can disrupt systemic inequities and create environments where diverse identities are valued and empowered.

Ultimately, intersectional leadership and solidarity among women in education are essential for creating inclusive systems that reflect our diverse communities. By honouring both the historical contributions of the white women who have been fighting against injustices within the system, and the voices and perspectives of racialized women, we can collectively challenge systemic barriers and transform schools into spaces of belonging and empowerment for all students.

Holding Hands for a Hopeful Future

In a time when white supremacy is resurging across the globe, it is crucial to recognize the many communities and individuals who have long resisted colonization and fought for liberation. Some have been so daring as to form biracial families, defying rigid racial classifications and creating identities that transcend simplistic categories. These families have lived their resistance in deeply embodied ways—seeking liberation, creativity, safety, and healing together. To overlook their sacred and personal commitments to an unknown future is to erase the very real and complex experiences of so many of the children we serve—children whose families have crossed cultural and national boundaries, carrying with them layers of history, language, and identity that cannot be reduced to narrow definitions.

To truly embrace intersectionality in educational leadership, we must reject a vision of education that settles for the hollowness of whiteness (Ahmed, 2007). Instead, we must rely on one another to critically examine what liberation means, what aspects of the system must be dismantled, and what must be reimaged. A transformative vision of education requires us to see healing as a call to action, to let love set the direction, and to recognize the land as a home for those willing to nurture it. This work demands that we align ourselves with all who share this greater vision, guided by the wisdom of Black and Indigenous leaders, moving forward with trust, compassion, patience, and clarity. As the late and brilliant Baldwin reminded us: “We’ve got to be as clear-headed about human beings as possible, because we are still each other’s only hope” (Mead & Baldwin, 1970).

Women in educational leadership, particularly those with complex intersectional identities, have long faced barriers—some stifled, others rising above them to become mentors for the next generation. Their stories and struggles form a tapestry of resilience, woven together to create a more just and hopeful future. Now, more than ever, we must serve diverse communities with complex needs and aspirations. No one person can be all things to all people. As a white woman, I, Sharlene, recognize that true leadership requires expanding my understanding and cultural competency by sharing space with others, like Carolina, whose lived experiences enrich my own. Being open to self-reflection and positionality, I have learned the value of true partnership in advancing equity. When we uplift the brilliance of racialized women and those who have been historically excluded from educational leadership, we all benefit—our children, our communities, and the generations to come.

As a Brazilian woman, I, Carolina, have witnessed firsthand the erosion of the publicly funded education system in my country through systemic defunding. I believe that Canada’s public education system is worth fighting for. But as Brazilians have learned through our long history of resisting genocide, slavery, and dictatorships, the only way forward is through solidarity—ninguém solta a mão de ninguém—“no one lets go of each other’s hands.” I deeply believe that the key to “holding on to each other’s hands” and undoing our current crises lies in being invested in mutual healing, fighting for each other’s liberation, and being open to a deeper understanding of our shared humanity. For all of that, we need education. As the Honourable Murray Sinclair so powerfully stated: “Education got us into this mess, and education is going to get us out” (Anderson, 2016).

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About the Authors

Bio: Carolina Miranda is a certified educator with the Ontario College of Teachers, whose dedication to a strong, publicly funded education system is evident in her commitment to fostering innovation and critical thinking for all students. With a Master of Education focused on women in educational leadership and as a current Ed.D. candidate she is researching intercultural competencies in K-12 school systems as per the Truth and Reconciliation Commission's Calls to Action. As an educator and administrator, she champions equity, inclusion, and innovative pedagogy, influencing both school and system-level initiatives. Originally from Brazil, Carolina immigrated to Canada in 2003 and has since laid roots in the Waterloo Region, a vibrant and diverse community. As a single mother and auntie, her personal experiences deeply shape her advocacy for children and her focus on nurturing cross-cultural relationships. She has been humbled by the kindness of colleagues like Sharlene who have supported her leadership journey in Ontario.

Bio: Sharlene McHolm has a Doctorate in Education Leadership and has been an administrator for 21 years. Her educator experience expands two countries, private and public educational systems, close custody schools and both panels. Her areas of specialization include mentorship, leadership development, neurodiverse learners and the implementation of TRC practices towards reconciliation. Sharlene is a 7th generation European settler raised on a farm in rural Ontario, Canada. Now living in urban South Western Ontario, Canada with her partner and two biracial children, Sharlene has had the support of many strong and wise women throughout her career. She considers herself fortunate to have intelligent colleagues such as Carolina Miranda to collaborate with and grow alongside.

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